

Deliverable 2.3.1 - Data Ingestion Workflow

Authors	George Caique Gouveia Barbosa, 0105w2p42
Status	published
DOI	10.5281/zenodo.20730680
Credit authorship contribution statement (CRediT¹)	George Caique Couveia Barbosa: Methodology, Software, Investigation, Writing - original draft. Sven Lieber: Data curation, Supervision, Project administration, Writing - reviewing & editing
Revision history	2025-11-07 - Document creation
	2026-06-17 - Adding GitHub link and publishing deliverable

¹ CRediT taxonomy <https://credit.niso.org/implementing-credit/>

License

© 2026 MetaBelgica. This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/legalcode.en>

Suggested citation

Barbosa, G.C.G, Lieber, S. (2026). Deliverable Deliverable 2.3.1 - Data Ingestion Workflow. MetaBelgica. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20730680>

Funding

Funded by the Belgian Science Policy Office (BELSPO) within the framework *Impulse action to fostering the development of emerging research infrastructures within federal research institutions* under the grant IM/RT/23/MetaBelgica

Contributing institutions

 Royal Museums
of Fine Arts of Belgium

Royal Institute for
Cultural Heritage

ROYAL MUSEUMS OF ART AND HISTORY
KONINKLIJKE MUSEA VOOR KUNST EN GESCHIEDENIS
MUSÉES ROYAUX D'ART ET D'HISTOIRE

IDLab
INTERNET & DATA LAB

1. Introduction

This report outlines the data ingestion strategy for MetaBelgica. The ingestion was designed to integrate entity data from four Belgian Federal Scientific Institutions (FSIs) into a Wikibase platform [2]. The project requires a robust data ingestion workflow, given that the data currently held by the four participating FSIs surpasses 1M entities.

In a previous step, the entity data was extracted and consolidated from the FSIs and stored in a columnar format. The ingestion pipeline reads the consolidated data, defines the schema, and inserts the entities as Wikibase items into their correct category.

2. System Architecture

The architecture follows a modular "Reader/Ingestor" pattern, designed to separate data parsing logic from API interaction. Each domain (Properties, Values, Geonames [3], Entities) is handled by a dedicated pair of components (Figure 1). The workflow enforces a dependency chain: structural elements (Properties and Values) are ingested first, followed by reference data (Geonames), and finally the Person entities.

Figure 1: The architecture of the ingestion pipeline.

3. Main modules and technologies

The system is written using Python, version 3.13. The main library used is the WikibaseIntegrator, version 0.12.13 [1]. WikibaseIntegrator is a wrapper to the Wikibase API, which is used to ingest entities with properties, values, and references that link the data back to its original source, ensuring data provenance. The source code is available at <https://github.com/MetaBelgica/data-ingestion>.

Orchestrator (CLI)

The CLI interface was built using the Cleo library [\[4\]](#), version 2.1.0, and serves as the main entry point to the ingestion process. Through the CLI, commands like `add-persons`, `add-geonames`, etc, are made available to the user. The person performing the data ingestion can use those commands to trigger each module and start the data ingestion process.

Authentication Module

Every insertion operation to the Wikibase instance must be authenticated. This module is responsible for handling the security. It manages credentials and passes active session tokens to the Ingestors. When using the ingestion script, it is required to define the user and password which will be used. This can be done by setting two environment variables: `WIKIBASE_USER` and `WIKIBASE_PASS`. Those can be set by changing the configuration file (`.env.yaml`).

3. Ingestion Pipeline Steps

The MetaBelgica data ingestion workflow uses a sequential pipeline that respects Wikibase knowledge graph dependencies. Properties and controlled vocabularies (Values) must be defined before they can describe geographical (Geonames) and core Person (Entities) entities. This ensures that all required structural components are in place before factual data is added, maintaining the integrity and consistency of the knowledge graph.

Properties

The Properties step defines the ontological structure of the Wikibase instance. Before any entity data is ingested, the system must define the predicates (properties) that will be used to describe those entities. This module ensures that all necessary properties are correctly configured. The two main components are the properties reader and ingestor.

The *PropertiesReader* class acts as an interface between the raw configuration data and the application logic. It reads from a CSV configuration file (`properties.csv`) that defines domain-specific properties such as “Birth date”, “Birth place”, or “Alternate Name”.

The reader automatically handles multilingual support by extracting labels in English, Dutch, and French. It also performs data type mapping, converting human-readable labels into specific WikibaseDatatype definitions (e.g., mapping “Birth date” to the Extended Date/Time Format (EDTF) and “Birth place” to WikibaseItem).

The *PropertiesIngestor* controls the creation of properties in the Wikibase instance. It combines the properties provided by the Reader with a set of hardcoded properties required for the system’s operation. These include:

1. External Identifiers: Properties for linking to external databases such as VIAF, ISNI, and the catalogs of the partner institutions (KBR, KIK-IRPA, etc.). These are configured with a “formatter URL” to ensure they are clickable in the UI.
2. System Flags: Internal properties used for workflow management, such as “visibility” (to toggle between internal/public records) and “record source”.
3. GeoNames Integration: Specific properties required to link entities to geographical data, such as coordinate locations and country references.

To improve performance, the Ingestor implements an idempotent design. It maintains a local cache mapping English labels to their corresponding Wikibase Property IDs. The caching system is based on a HashMap. Before creating a new property, the system checks this cache to prevent the creation of duplicate properties, reducing API overhead during repeated runs.

Values

The values step establishes the concepts that exist within the system. This module creates the items (instances) that serve as the controlled vocabulary for the knowledge graph. These items are assigned QIDs (Wikibase Item IDs) and are used for classifying imported entities and tracking their provenance.

Among the concepts ingested, there are workflow and visibility flags, ontological classes and institutional sources. Items such as “public visibility” and “internal visibility” are created to manage data access levels. These allow the system to flag records that are cleared for public release versus those restricted to back-office use (e.g., for GDPR compliance). The module also creates core classes required for semantic classification, such as “human,” “country,” and “city.” These items serve as the targets for the “instance of” property, allowing the system to categorize imported entities. Specific items are generated to represent the four contributing Federal Scientific Institutions (KBR, KIK-IRPA, KMSKB, KMKG).

The *ValuesIngestor* mirrors the idempotent design of the Properties step. It uses the HashMap cache to map English labels to their existing QIDs.

Geonames

The geonames step is responsible for populating the knowledge graph with standardized geographical entities. The work is divided into two steps: data parsing and ingestion.

The list of countries comes from a TSV file containing country metadata (Figure 2). There’s an aggregation logic to combine multiple rows sharing the same geoname_id. This allows the system to construct a single country object containing multilingual aliases (English, Dutch, French, German) and ISO codes.

The list of cities comes from a CSV file containing city and region data. It extracts essential attributes including coordinates (latitude/longitude), population data, and localized names, converting them into standardized GeoNamesEntry objects.

Figure 2: Representation of the input CSV file for the ingestion pipeline

GeonamesRecord
+int geonamesID +string countryCode +string nameDefault +string nameEN +string nameNL +string nameFR +string nameDE +int population +float latitude +float longitude

The ingestion step manages the insertion of these entities into Wikibase. The operations are done by inserting countries first. This is necessary because city items must link to their respective countries to be semantically valid. Later on, when a city is ingested, the system resolves its `country_code` against the cache of previously created country items. This allows the ingestion script to create a direct semantic link (using the “country” property) between the city and its parent nation. The same caching strategy from the previous steps is applied.

Entities

The entities step reads the clustered data into Person entities within the knowledge graph. This module is responsible for consolidating data from multiple sources (KBR, KIK-IRPA, KMSKB, KMKG) into a single WikibaseItem. The input for this process is a pre-integrated CSV file (Figure 3) where records have already been grouped into clusters by a previous reconciliation process. The *PersonsReader* parses this file into cluster objects. Each cluster represents a single real-world person but can contain multiple data records, one for each institution that holds data on that individual. This structure allows the system to aggregate information. For example, one institution might provide the birth date, while another provides the death place or an alternate name.

The *PersonsIngestor* converts these clusters into Wikibase items, while guaranteeing a few premises. First, every statement added to the graph (whether it is a birth date, an external ID, or a name alias) is referenced. The ingestion script checks which institution provided a specific piece of data and attaches a “reference” block linking back to the original institution’s Person ID. The system also links the new entity to international authority files (ISNI, VIAF) and the internal catalogs of the participating FSIs. Birth and death places are not stored as simple strings. Instead, the ingestor resolves the `geoname_id` provided in the source data against the local cache created by the Geonames step, linking the person directly to the corresponding City item.

Figure 3: Representation of the input CSV file for the ingestion pipeline

4. Performance

The ingestion workflow's performance was measured across its sequential steps to assess the time required for initial setup and the subsequent entity ingestion phases. The total time elapsed is highly dependent on the volume of data and the number of concurrent processes used for the most intensive step, *Add persons*.

Step-by-Step Performance Metrics

Table 1 summarizes the execution time for the initial, structural setup steps (*Properties*, *Values*, and *Geonames*) based on a test run.

Table 1: Ingestion time per step

Step	Operation	Total Time Elapsed
Properties	Properties	3.13 seconds
Values	Items	1.33 seconds
Geonames	Geonames	564.51 seconds (approx. 9 minutes)

Entity Ingestion Performance

The most data intensive step is the *Add persons* module. This step was tested under multiple concurrency settings to determine the optimal throughput, measured in records per second (r/s) and estimated time to ingest 1 million (1M) entities.

Table 2: Throughput per multithread setting

Concurrency	Throughput (r/s)	Estimated Time to Ingest 1M Entities
Serial (1 Thread)	7.61	36 hours
10 Threads	19.51	14.23 hours
14 Threads	25.70	10.77 hours
20 Threads	26.30	10.56 hours

Table 2 shows that using multithreading reduces the ingestion time for the full dataset from 36 hours (serial) to approximately 10.5 hours (20 threads). The performance ceiling is reached between 14 and 20 threads, suggesting that increasing the thread count beyond the number of available vCPUs (14 in the test environment) yields diminishing returns due to API rate limits and network latency.

5. Limitations and Future work

The current ingestion workflow is limited to Person entities and requires a pre-integrated, denormalized CSV as input. Future work will focus on expanding the system's capabilities to handle other data inputs (e.g., different properties, different input file structures) and a functionality to handle updates. Enhancements to the ingestion Pipeline will include support for situations where the location is not precisely defined.

References

- [1] LeMyst. (2026). *WikibaseIntegrator: A Python library for interacting with Wikibase instances* [Computer software]. GitHub. <https://github.com/LeMyst/WikibaseIntegrator>
- [2] Wikimedia Deutschland. (2026). *Wikibase: Software for structured data*. Wikibase. Retrieved January 8, 2026, from <https://wikiba.se/>
- [3] GeoNames. (2026). *GeoNames geographical database*. Retrieved January 8, 2026, from <https://www.geonames.org/>
- [4] Python Poetry. (2025). *Cleo: Create beautiful and testable command-line interfaces* [Computer software]. GitHub. <https://github.com/python-poetry/cleo>